

Triumphs and Trials: Experiences of university scholars in international journal publishing

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ABSTRACT

Publishing in international journals is essential for advancing knowledge, addressing societal concerns, and enhancing academic visibility. However, the publication process presents both opportunities and challenges for university scholars. This study explored the triumphs, struggles, and motivations of university scholars in publishing in international journals using a qualitative case study design. The findings indicated that university scholars' experiences in their triumphs in publishing internationally are rewarding, expand the writer's credentials, provide a more comprehensive understanding of social issues, promote high morale and honor, improve writing and pedagogical philosophy, develop technical skills in exploring interweaving ideas, improve communication, fuel perseverance, and provide fulfillment. Despite these achievements, scholars encountered significant challenges, including difficulties in literature review development, conceptual framing, and academic language proficiency. Technological constraints, such as unstable internet connectivity and limited access to research resources, further impeded productivity. Personal and psychological challenges—including time management pressures, financial limitations, stress, and emotional strain—also affected the publication process. Environmental distractions likewise disrupted sustained writing momentum. Notwithstanding these obstacles, scholars remained motivated by mentorship support, professional recognition, career advancement aspirations, and a commitment to contributing meaningful knowledge to society. The study recommends strengthening institutional support through structured recognition programs, clear research award criteria, the establishment of a dedicated research hub, and expanded access to training and international research engagement opportunities to foster a sustainable research culture.

Keywords: International journal, University scholars, Triumphs, Struggles, Motivation

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving academic landscape, curiosity and inquiry remain essential drivers of knowledge creation, while strong research skills are critical for achieving scholarly success. At the same time, the pressure to publish frequently—often described as the “publish or perish” culture—continues to shape the priorities and behaviors of researchers, compelling them to maintain high levels of productivity even under challenging conditions (Callaghan, 2016; van Dalen, 2021). This has contributed to the rapid growth of global academic publications, placing increasing pressure on journals, peer reviewers, and the sustainability of scholarly communication systems (Hanson et al., 2023). Scholars have increasingly highlighted ethical, qualitative, and systematic challenges posed by this environment, prompting discussions on the sustainability and reform of research practices worldwide (Quia, 2025; Bayanbayeva, 2025).

Internationally, Phothongsunan (2016) identified three types of difficulties faced by students: discursive, non-discursive, and other. Discourse issues involve language and context, while non-discursive problems involve motivation, emotional and psychological issues, and plagiarism. Addressing journal publication issues requires a diverse approach to resolving complex issues. In the Philippines, private and public colleges and universities must show a solid commitment to knowledge creation through research (Wambaleka, 2015). However, writing is challenging for everyone, let alone someone who writes in a second or third language (Xiong, 2022). Academic writing dysfunction is a well-known problem that is not to be taken lightly; research shows that time and emotions are the root causes of the issue (Belcher et al., 2015).

Recent studies emphasize that academic publishing remains a central component of higher education, shaped by increasing global competition, digital transformation, and institutional expectations. The persistent emphasis on publication output continues to influence research productivity, particularly among early-career scholars navigating

complex editorial and peer-review processes (Hanson et al., 2023; Hill, 2025). At the same time, the expansion of digital research tools and open-access platforms has transformed scholarly communication, enabling wider dissemination but also intensifying publication pressure and quality demands. Scholars are now required to demonstrate strong research design academic writing proficiency, and adaptability in a rapidly evolving academic environment (Curry & Lillis, 2021; Murray, 2022). As a result, student researchers must develop strong research design skills, academic writing proficiency, and adaptability in order to succeed in a rapidly changing academic environment.

These developments suggest that, beyond personal readiness, academic and institutional factors play a crucial role in shaping students' success in completing and publishing scholarly work. Despite these growing demands, limited research has explored the lived experiences of student researchers who have successfully published in international journals. Therefore, this study sought to explore in greater depth the experiences of university scholars at Mindanao State University-General Santos City who published in international journals. This study holds significant social and academic importance, as it may enable scholars to address various societal issues and concerns more effectively through the writing and publication of research papers.

1.1. Research questions

This study aimed to investigate the University scholars' struggles and triumphs in writing and publishing in international journals. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the university scholars in their triumphs on publishing their scholarly works?
2. What are the struggles of student scholars on publishing?
3. What motivates student scholars on publishing their scholarly works?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

An international journal is one in which most of the editorial board members and reviewers do not live in the country where the journal's headquarters are situated. international journals must have a good reputation, be well-read, and be accessible to many scholars worldwide. Writing for academic journals requires a structured approach and a clear understanding of publication expectations, including formatting, organization, and audience awareness (Murray, 2022).

2.1. Motivations and benefits for scholarly publishing

Writing for scholarly publications has several benefits for university students. The study of Smiles and Short (2006) shows that writing for publication provides many professional benefits for teachers, researchers, and the academic community. Still, the process from drafting a research paper to actual publication is challenging. Based on the findings, 29% of the authors experienced stress while striving to follow the format of an article, since it is a complex and even unpleasant chore for some of them. Three percent said they had issues with reviewers but eventually understood them; the remaining three percent said dealing with varied standards was challenging because "occasionally assessors have diverse criteria, and it is difficult to determine which road to pursue". The study's findings suggest five key motivations for submitting articles, namely: contributing to the profession, journal recognition, their desire to accomplish a goal, the assurance of receiving assistance in such an attempt, and some practical motivations. Above all, the major motivator is the belief that they can and should contribute to the profession as teachers. Our participants, like Smiles and Short (2006), demonstrated that their decision to publish an article was to inform the field by presenting an intellectual or expert perspective. Study revealed that interest is still another strong motivator. Accordingly, it serves two main purposes: it influences students' goals, particularly if they see writing as a means of satisfying their communication needs (Csikszentmihalyi & Rathunde, 2000).

Furthermore, research shows that one of the benefits of publishing international journals is that they may readily engage with others for academic purposes and for people who are interested in the same research topics. The participants most frequently highlighted the benefits of publishing as a preparation for academic career and having competitive advantage in the job market. Most people require much experience before their work improves to the point where their papers are approved by prestigious academic publications. As a result, the more pupils write, the more probable their papers will be of higher quality. Moreover, getting published, even in lower-status journals, may be extremely exciting and rewarding for students, promoting their professional growth and pushing them to produce more and better articles. (Wilkins et al. 2021).

Researchers play a crucial role in discovering novel treatments and ensuring that current treatments are applied as effectively as possible. They can fill in information gaps, uncover mysteries, and alter how healthcare practitioners conduct their work. The process of community development employs research as a tool (Barr, 2005). These viewpoints suggest very distinct power dynamics between community psychologists and the populations they work with, as well as very different attitudes toward research (Barr, 2005).

2.2. Challenges in academic writing and publication

Researchers—especially early-career scholars—face various challenges, including balancing multiple roles, meeting publication requirements, and responding to peer review feedback, although institutional support and mentorship can significantly aid in achieving success (SAGE Publishing, 2023; Curry & Lillis, 2021). Writing journals is hard work for everyone. There is no easy way to do so. However, having a structured approach and an understanding of what is required is reasonable. The specific steps to writing are a separate topic found in other articles and publications (Belcher, 2021). Additionally, in the Philippine context, these challenges are compounded by infrastructural and technological barriers. Studies have shown that students engaged in remote and research-based learning frequently encounter unstable internet connections, lack of appropriate devices, and limited access to scholarly materials, which impede their ability to conduct write research effectively (Toquero, 2020a; Toquero, 2020b). Indeed, many challenges are faced by researchers. However, balancing all aspects of a new role can be overwhelming.

According to many researchers there had been problems related to organization and structure of the paper, definition of the topic, the literature review, etc. Undergraduate students involved in this study reported initial anxiety and lack of confidence when they first wrote their first drafts of research papers. Once the research was completed, researchers felt accomplished. Al-Mukdad (2019), in his study "Investigating English Academic Writing Problems Encountered by Arab International University Students," indicated that respondents find the process of research writing rigorous. The participants of the said study are students of Arab International University who take the Applied Wave Research (AWR) course. The survey revealed that 46% of students admitted that they could brainstorm, particularly if they are interested with the chosen topic, while 92% had difficulty organizing their thoughts. Different researchers tend to cite the same problems, namely, the organization and structure of the paper, definition of the topic, and literature review. The majority of the studies reviewed tied language skills with academic writing. There are limited writings about the challenges faced by undergraduate students in completing various sections of their thesis.

Furthermore, emerging research highlights that academic integrity is not uniformly demonstrated across all sections of student writing but varies depending on the cognitive demands of the task. For instance, a study on pre-service teachers written outputs revealed that while students generally exhibit high levels of academic writing, they tend to struggle more in sections requiring critical thinking, synthesis, and proper citation—particularly in the body of academic contexts (Arroyo et al., 2026). This observation is consistent with the findings of Espinosa and Toquero (2018), who reported that although pre-service teachers self-reported high levels of academic integrity, challenges in paraphrasing, citing sources, and analyzing literature persist, often leading to unintentional academic misconduct. This suggests that difficulties in academic writing is not simply due to lack of awareness, but also stem from students' insufficient mastery of higher-order writing skills. As such, there is a need for more focused instructional support that goes beyond raising awareness about plagiarism and instead helps students strengthen their ability to paraphrase, integrate sources, and develop original arguments. In the end, communicating complex ideas in school or in the workplace requires not only technical accuracy but also clarity, accessibility, and the ability to respond to the needs of the audience (Sarad et al., 2026).

2.3. Institutional support and writing development strategies

Many supports exist that can help individuals become successful. Institutional and instructional supports play a crucial role in academic writing and publication skills (Murray, 2022). In the context of contemporary higher education, there is an increasing recognition of the need for inclusive and responsive support systems that address both academic and socio-emotional needs of learners. For instance, Toquero (2021) emphasizes that higher education institutions must adopt flexible, inclusive, and student-centered strategies to ensure that learners can effectively engage in academic tasks despite external constraints.

Similarly, Dubicki (2015) suggested a variety of ways for faculty members to help novice student-researchers cope with research-related challenges. Specifically, these include: (1) collaborating with librarians on assignments; (2) scaffolding assignments for early intervention in case problems will arise; (3) bringing courses to the library for instruction; and (4) motivating student-researchers to meet with librarians for one-on-one mentoring. In addition to these strategies, instructional practices that model effective writing are equally important. For example, incorporating activities that utilize critiqued writing samples—particularly in complex sections such as the discussion section—can help students better understand the conventions of academic writing (Ling, 2013).

2.4. Conceptual framework

Writing well is a skill that scholars must develop throughout their academic endeavors. Aspiring university scholars may find writing for and publishing in foreign publications challenging. Hence, this study was founded on the psychological concept of self-determination theory, which explains people's volitional acts that are motivated by their own will. Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (SDT) defines self-determination as motivating elements and the influence of self-determined autonomy and motivation on students' education and learning. This demonstrated how crucial it is for all individual and social functioning to fulfill people's basic requirements for competence, relatedness, and autonomy (Deci & Ryan, 2017).

Self-determination Theory (SDT) is a theory of human motivation and personality that proposes that people may become self-sufficient when their needs for competence, relatedness, and autonomy are met. Self-determined behavior results from deliberate, conscious choices and decisions. This idea can assist us comprehend what motivates a particular individual's actions. Given the importance of self-determination in achieving independence, this idea is critical to an individual's overall well-being and psychological health. Self-determination puts the individual in control, making them both accountable and possibly guilty for whatever happens. Given this, self-determination has a significant influence on motivation. If the individuals believe they can manage themselves properly, they will likely find more motivation in whatever task they wish to carry out (Garrido, 2023). Furthermore, self-determination theory attempts to explain how being self-determined influences motivation—people are more driven to take action when they believe what they do will affect the result. This notion has been utilized in a variety of contexts, including education, employment, parenting, exercise, and health. According to research, high levels of self-determination can lead to success in a variety of areas of life. In school, self-determined children are more likely to be driven to succeed. They also tend to experience higher levels of competence and happiness. Self-determination may be critical to how people operate in many different aspects of their life. Feeling in control and organically driven might make individuals feel more devoted, enthusiastic, engaged, and happy with what they do (Cherry, 2023).

The Self-determination Theory (SDT) method offers a thorough framework for explanation that pertains to three aspects of behavior and motivation in an efficient manner. It begins by outlining the causes and predictors of exercise behavior, which include personal factors (such as basic psychological need satisfaction) and environmental factors (such as rewards, informational feedback, and instruction style) that influence motivational style or regulation in exercise contexts, as well as significant psychological outcomes like intentions and perceived competence. Another goal is to illustrate how the antecedent constructs influence mediation, moderation, behavior, and other important results.

Consequently, the Self-determination Theory (SDT) seeks to explain behavior and motivation using individual variations in interpersonal perceptions, environmental factors, and motivational orientations. Thus, this theory helped this study to emphasize what motivates university scholars to publish in international journals. The challenges they have encountered and the experiences that brought them triumphs in publishing in international journals.

Figure 1 shows the study's conceptual framework, representing university scholars' triumphs and struggles in their research journey. To analyze the data gathered, the researchers broke down this particular variable into different themes to better understand and gain in-depth knowledge about the topic. Thus, the researchers came up with three overall themes for the study. These are triumphs, struggles, and motivations. Hence, the sub-themes lie within the extracted theme from the data gathered.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the study

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Design

This study aimed to understand the triumphs and struggles of university scholars publishing in international journals. The researchers used qualitative research methods, specifically the case study approach. A case study is an in-depth analysis of a particular topic, such as an individual, group, location, occasion, organization, or phenomena. Case studies are useful for characterizing, contrasting, assessing, and comprehending many facets of a study issue (McCombes, 2019). Hence, qualitative methods seek insights into the perspective and meaning of experiences and the social structures or processes that explain people's behavior. Most importantly, Qualitative research is used to understand how people experience the world (Bhandari, 2020). Therefore, in order to get specialized, contextual, and in-depth knowledge about a particular real-world issue, a case study was an acceptable research strategy employed in this study. It made it possible for scholars to investigate the case's salient features, significance, and ramifications (McCombes, 2022). The researchers sought to better understand the university scholars' triumphs and struggles in publishing in international journals.

Figure 2: The Research Design of the Study

3.2. Population

The participants of this study comprised twelve university scholars enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) program at Mindanao State University–General Santos City, Philippines, who had prior experience publishing in international journals. These scholars also participated in the International Conference on Research in Educational Sciences (ICRES) in 2022, a research conference organized by the College of Education of the same university. Their participation contributed to the academic recognition of the institution, particularly the BEED Department. Furthermore, their scholarly endeavors were formally acknowledged through the conferment of the Papyrus Prize—an annual recognition event organized by *The Papyrus*, the official journalism organization of the College of Education, which honors outstanding university scholars within the college. Their research outputs were likewise published in international journals indexed in Google Scholar.

3.3. Sampling and sampling technique

This study employed purposive population sampling as its sampling technique. Purposive sampling, also referred to as judgment sampling, involves the deliberate selection of participants based on specific characteristics that align with the objectives of the study. The researchers utilized purposive sampling to ensure that participants possessed direct and meaningful experience in publishing in international journals, which is central to the purpose of the investigation. Purposive sampling is commonly used in qualitative research, where the goal is to obtain in-depth insights into a particular phenomenon rather than to produce statistical generalizations (McCombes, 2019). Accordingly, the selected university scholars from the BEED Department of the College of Education were intentionally chosen to provide rich and relevant data for this research endeavor.

3.4. Research locale

This study was conducted at Mindanao State University–General Santos City, focusing specifically on university scholars from the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) Department under the College of Education. These scholars had experience publishing in international journals and had participated in the International Conference on Research in Education and Science (ICRES). The university takes pride in its active engagement in research and extension initiatives at the international level, consistent with its tri-focal functions of instruction, research, and extension. Through these initiatives, the institution has established partnerships and gained recognition from countries such as Australia, Bangladesh, Ghana, Monaco, and Malaysia.

Moreover, university scholars from this institution have produced research outputs recognized for their quality and contributions to both the academic community and service sectors. Given the presence of approximately 24 university scholars who had engaged in international journal publication, the university was deemed an appropriate research locale for this study. However, only 12 scholars met the inclusion criteria and consented to participate. Their relevant experiences in publishing in international journals provided rich and meaningful data that supported the attainment of the study's objective—to gain a deeper understanding of the triumphs and challenges encountered by university scholars in publishing in international journals.

3.5. Instrumentation

In this study, the researchers developed a set of guide questions that served as the primary research instrument for data collection. These interview questions were carefully constructed to elicit detailed and relevant responses aligned with the objectives of the study. To facilitate data collection, the researchers utilized an online platform by creating a Google Form through which the prepared questions were distributed to the selected university scholars of Mindanao State University who had experience publishing in international journals. The participants submitted their responses through the same platform. Subsequently, the researchers systematically organized and analyzed the collected data to generate meaningful findings relevant to the study's purpose.

3.6. Data gathering procedure

The primary objective of this study was to gain a deeper understanding of the triumphs and struggles experienced by twelve university scholars from the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) program in publishing in international journals. In adherence to ethical considerations, the researchers first secured a list of eligible university scholars and formally sought their consent to participate in the study. Only those who voluntarily agreed were included in the data-gathering process.

Upon obtaining informed consent, the researchers implemented the selected data-gathering technique by distributing a Google Form containing the structured guide questions. The online platform was chosen due to its accessibility, efficiency, and suitability for collecting written responses aligned with the nature of the research instrument. The Google Form included the study title, its purpose, and a brief explanation of the research objectives to ensure that participants were fully informed before responding.

To facilitate systematic data management, all members of the research team were granted collaborator access to the Google Form. This ensured proper monitoring, organization, and retrieval of responses for transcription and analysis. All submitted responses were carefully collected, compiled into a secure file document, and stored in Google Drive to maintain data organization and security. The researchers then transcribed the responses in the order in which they were submitted.

Participants were provided with secure access to the Google Form link, which was distributed through their Messenger accounts for convenience. The structured guide questions enabled the researchers to remain focused on the objectives of the study while allowing participants sufficient flexibility to share their experiences comprehensively. The use of an online platform facilitated efficient data collection, organization, and transcription in preparation for data analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis systematically applies logical methods to explain, demonstrate, and analyze observational patterns throughout the data-gathering process (Savenye, 2004). In a broad sense, qualitative data analysis gives a data set context (Anfara et al. 2002). Qualitative data includes a variety of elements (e.g., conversational data, photographs, observations, and unstructured, semi-structured, or structured interviews, among others). Since qualitative data analysis is often linked to a particular technique, theoretical viewpoint, research tradition, and area, it may really relate to a variety of things (Lochmiller & Lester, 2017).

Thus, the researchers utilized qualitative thematic analysis to analyze the data gathered, allowing them to divide and categorize massive quantities of data efficiently. Thematic analysis is helpful when looking for personally identifiable information, such as participants' experiences, viewpoints, and opinions. It is typically based on data from surveys, social media posts, interviews, and conversations (Crosley, 2021). Thematic analysis is a study of meaning patterns. In other words, it is necessary to analyze the themes in your database to determine their purpose. Most importantly, because the research questions guide this process, it was not necessary to identify every possible theme in the data but rather to concentrate on the crucial components of the survey questions. Hence, after the researchers pointed out the approach needed, they followed the thematic analysis process. Braun & Clarke (2006) provide a six-phase guide and a practical framework for conducting this kind of analysis.

Figure 3. Six basic phases of thematic data analysis by Braun & Clarke (2006)

This six-phase thematic analysis method of Braun and Clarke guided the researchers in creating themes for each of the study's variables. The researchers found three (3) variables linked to the research questions or statements of the problem of the study; these are; triumphs, struggles, and motivation of university scholars on publishing in international journals. These steps guided each variable's themes throughout the analysis process/stage.

Phase 1. Become familiar with the data - Learning the full data set requires active and frequent reading of the data, which is the initial stage in the theme analysis process (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Although it may be tempting to start coding data and looking for themes right away, familiarizing oneself with the complete data set is essential for all following processes and will offer helpful direction to the raw data (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). The researchers in this phase transcribed all the data gathered from Google Forms. Through transcription of the data, the researchers could be fully immersed and actively engaged in the data. They read and re-read the transcripts and list initial thoughts to spot similar themes. This was the guide in organizing the final data summary.

Phase 2. Generate Initial Codes - Data coding is the process of creating meaningful categories straight from gathered data. Observations, interviews, and questionnaires are frequently used in qualitative research to collect data. The primary purpose of coding is to discover and document the major concepts and underlying meanings presented by participants. Researchers start by creating preliminary codes based on recurrent patterns or key assertions, which are then refined and organized to ensure they are clear, accurate, and indicative of the data. With some circumstances, codes may be given numerical values to aid with analysis and interpretation. Finally, data coding involves more than just decreasing enormous volumes of information; it is also about carefully structuring it while preserving all critical insights. In this phase, the researchers tried to organize the thoughts and responses of the participants linked to each study's variable to make coding easier and more flexible. The researchers begin finding the same words and phrases among the responses of the university scholars' depending upon the variables of this study. Then they generated initial codes using Microsoft Highlighter to quickly identify and determine the phrases and words with the same meaning (Data Coding in Research Methodology, 2014).

Phase 3. Search for Themes - As stated before, it is a pattern that captures an important or instructive aspect of the data and study issue. This stage entails going over the coded and compiled data extracts to search for any themes of wider relevance, as stated by Braun & Clarke (2006). Furthermore, there are no strict guidelines for what constitutes a theme, as Braun & Clarke (2006) clarify. The relevance of a topic defines it. There could be a lot of overlap between this step of finding preliminary themes and the coding stage if you have a small data collection (such as one brief focus group). In this case, the researchers searched the categories and themes from the extracted codes highlighted in the second phase of the analysis process and examined the codes to fit into a theme.

Phase 4. Review Themes - In this section, the researchers examined whether the themes applied to both the coded extracts and the complete data set (Braun & Clarke, 2006). As a result, this step entails examining the coded data that has been extracted. Thus, after reading all of the compiled excerpts for every subject, the researchers evaluated whether or not they seemed to follow a logical pattern. The validity of each topic in relation to the data set was then examined by the researchers (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The basic themes found in Step 3 were examined, adjusted, and expanded upon by the researchers throughout this step. It is advisable to gather relevant data for every subject at this stage.

Phase 5. Define Themes - Finding the "essence" of each topic is the goal of this last stage of theme refining (Braun & Clarke, 2006). At this stage, the researchers examined the data inside the themes to define and improve them for analysis. Each topic's essence was chosen by the researchers, who also ascertained which part of the data each theme captured.

Phase 6. Writing-up - Research culminates in a report, usually a dissertation or journal article. This stage includes the final examination of each subject as it is where the report is produced. Instead of merely being paraphrased or described, the facts in this section have been examined, understood, and made meaning of, claim Braun and Clarke (2006). As a result, the researchers examined the theme in light of a clear, succinct, and captivating narrative that the data revealed. They evaluate the findings in the context of pertinent research, theories, and study-related ideas.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Findings

This chapter presents and discusses the results, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered from the twelve (12) university scholars from the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) Department of Mindanao State University-General Santos City. Results were consequently presented using tables with the data gathered from the participants. The findings of this study help better understand the three (3) variables linked to the research questions or statements of the problem of the study; these are; triumphs, struggles, and motivations of university scholars in writing and publishing in international journals. Hence, the data collection will follow a six-phase guide of thematic analysis by Braun and Clark (2006). These are (1) **become familiar with the data**, (2) **generate initial codes**, (3) **search for themes**, (4) **review themes**, (5) **define themes**, and (6) **writing-up**.

		n	%
Gender			
	Women	9	37.5%
	Men	15	62.5%
Year Publish			
	2021	6	50%
	2022	6	50%
No. of Publications	No. of Authors	Total no. of authors in 12 Articles	%
Article 1	2	24	100%
Article 2	16		
Article 3	2		
Article 4	16		
Article 5	3		
Article 6	3		
Article 7	2		
Article 8	2		
Article 9	3		
Article 10	3		
Article 11	2		
Article 12	4		
Attended research webinars	Yes	24	100%
	No	0	0

Table 1: University scholars' profile on publishing in international journals

The table above indicates the 24 University Scholars' who published internationally. Prior to that, the researchers used a table to organize their backgrounds and better grasp their identities and journals. There are 9 (37.5%) female and 15 (62.5%) male university scholars. There are 12 articles published. Every article indicated the number of authors. Some authors had 2-3 journals published. With that, a total of 24 university scholars published their journals. In 2021, there are 6 (50%) journals published, and in 2022, there are 6 (50%) journals published. All 24 (100%) University Scholars attended research webinars—however, only 12 University Scholars' who had participated in this study. Moving on, these university scholars have credibly published their international journals, which can be found in Google Scholar and can

reach the broadest possible audience.

SOP 1. What are the experiences of the university scholars in their triumphs on publishing in international journals?

Figure 5. Overview of the themes of university scholars’ experiences in their triumphs on publishing in international journals

Rewarding

Publishing in international journals has become an avenue for university scholars to be recognized not just as papyrus awardees in the college but also for their scholarly works, which have been recognized in the wider scope of the research community online, which begets recognition and authority. Hence, university scholars gained rewards and recognition for publishing in international journals. The data shows that 36% of the university scholars said that publishing gives them an opportunity for recognition and honor. They also received a certificate of recognition, which gives them an opportunity to be referenced and recognized; 18% for being referred; 9% as it gives them credibility as the author's name appears on their work; and 9% as it boosts university scholars’ confidence.

“The opportunities we have received was recognition” [P#1]

“Recognition is one of the incentives we get aside from the money and tokens. Happy to know that commendations and appreciation are also present for giving us strength and courage to continue writing article” [P#2]

“The incentive that was given to us is recognition from the College of Education and the official publication The Papyrus as the first recipients of "The Papyrus Prize: Young Scholar Award in Research” [P#8]

One of the university scholar’s significant triumphs in publishing in an international journal is getting a reward because they gained recognition and incentives from their college. This kind of reward gave strength and courage to the university scholar to continue writing an article, and they are now a source of ideas for imparting knowledge to other researchers.

“This published international journal allowed our written work to be accessed, utilized for purpose and become available for a wider scope of research community through online. And this helps academic scholars and anyone interested, for their collection of additional references.” [P#3]

Aside from recognition, university scholars’ journals can be accessible online and become available to a wider scope of the research community. It truly means that after the university scholars published their paper, they became authors, which serves as a reference for another researcher.

“The incentives of university scholar who writes and published international journals are given awards of recognition together with a small amount of money as a token of appreciation. We were given a medal, certificate and an honorarium.” [P#8]

In addition to the rewards obtained by the university scholars, they also get incentives in the form of cash, medals, and certificates. It was given to them by the college as recognition for their hard work and excellence.

Expands the Writers' Credentials

Since publishing in international journals was an arduous process for the university scholars, its results satisfied them, and they contributed to finding solutions to emerging social issues through having published research not just locally but internationally. Meanwhile, this endeavor expands the writers' credentials, allowing them to become known as authors, and it adds value to their academic endeavors and professional development.

"I think the benefits of writing and publishing international journals is our work was discoverable by other readers." [P#4]

"It improves and adds value to the list of our credentials and academic background." [P#7]

Publishing an international journal has also become an avenue for university scholars to share their scholarly works in a broader sense. It became easily accessible, and it can be an additional source of supporting data for other researchers. Further, it expands their credentials as their experience gives them authority, which also adds significant value to their professional development.

"As it penetrates wider audience or wider research community online, it becomes easily accessible to all and thus help others to gather more data as our work can be an additional and supporting data that relates to their own work. Another benefit is expanding our credentials, as these experiences add value to our professional background" [P#10]

Technical Skills in Exploring Interweaving Ideas

Writing in academia requires technical skills in exploring interweaving ideas so that the purpose of the paper is comprehensible and can reach a wider audience in the research community. Through publishing in international journals, 25% of university scholars find benefits in the process of making their scholarly works because it improves their writing skills, critical thinking skills, research skills, and ability to afford reliable knowledge and ideas to address to social issues.

"I actually contributed in writing a journal and it was then published internationally. Though, I am only a contributor, it helped me in improving my writing skills, be more critical, and applied it in writing our undergraduate thesis and other academic works." [P#4]

"For me, knowledge is one of the benefits we can get from writing and publishing international journals. Since you need to study everything to get a good scope to improve and enhance your write ups. Also, we will be recognized not just locally but internationally." [P#2]

As a matter of fact, through publishing in international journals, university scholars broaden their perspectives in a broader sense of the research community. They can be able to view other perspectives and dig up more information that helps solve social issues. Along with the process, university scholars find it very challenging, but it helps them explore many ideas that expand their thinking capacities.

"By widening my understanding in some aspect and it really develop my research skill to view other perspective." [P#1]

"It taught me to not settle for less and to dig more information to help me make my paper more reliable." [P#10]

"I learned new techniques in writing along the process of creating the journal. And it challenges us to expand thinking capacity through exploring ideas and concepts that majority of the people could relate." [P#3]

"The benefit of writing and publishing international journals is the chance to present my ideas and contribute to the body of knowledge during these precarious times." [P#5]

Improving writing and pedagogical philosophy

Pedagogy refers to the way of teaching students, both theoretically and practically. There is a relationship between learning methods and cultural practices. Building on the knowledge pupils have already acquired, pedagogy works to help students enhance their abilities and attitudes. Through publishing international journals, it helps university scholars improve their writing and be more effective in teaching since it is an essential part of the teaching and learning process. This endeavor improves the university scholars' pedagogy as well as their philosophy of teaching. Hence, 8% of the university scholars said that writing for an international journal improved their writing and pedagogical philosophy.

“Developing writing and publishing scholarly works can strengthen the capacity of teachers to be more effective in teaching, since writing is an essential part of teaching and learning process.” [P#3]

“It improves my pedagogy as well as my philosophy in teaching.” [P#5]

However, publishing an international journal taught university scholars to realize that teaching has a wider scope and does not only focus on teaching learners but is also an agent of change in all aspects that are disseminated to the academy and other stakeholders.

“It helps me realize that teaching is indeed a wide scope. Not only to focus only on the learners itself but the overall aspects that may distribute an effect on the academe of each learner and other stakeholders.” [P#7]

Further, university scholars proved that through publishing an international journal, it taught them to develop their character as teachers by being patient, which can be put to good use in their chosen career. It also enables them to build their personal and professional collaboration, ethics, philosophy, and developmental goals.

“As I mentioned in response to the previous question, writing and publishing research teaches me patience, which I can put to good use in my chosen career of teaching. In addition, the journal that we publish will enable me to develop ways of educating my students.” [P#11]

“It builds my personal and professional collaboration, ethics, philosophy, and developmental goals.” [P#9]

High morale, Honor

Having recognition not just locally but internationally gives an extra mile of positive impact to the College of Education at Mindanao State University since this is the first time that this institution produces young researchers for international journals. Thus, three (25%) university scholars stated these achievements. This achievement brings high morale and honor to the college or department because it emphasizes the good management and competent culture of the college, which attracts opportunities as stakeholders could be drawn to these achievements.

“It raised the morale of the department and college. Got recognized that its students have the ability to publish journals internationally and compete with other researchers.” [P#4]

“I believe it instills in other students a sense of enthusiasm and determination to write and publish a journal that will bring pride and admiration to the college or department with the guidance of Ma'am Cathy.” [P#11]

“Oh, it really develops the college and department because it becomes well know that produces young researchers.” [P#12]

“Students' accomplishments can also be a reflection of the departments culture. It brings pride and honor to the department, emphasizing the good management and competent culture of the college. It can also boost the positive image and enhance the status of department. It can attract more opportunities as stakeholders could be drawn to these achievements.” [P#3]

In addition, publishing in an international journal is not for everyone. Hence, the university scholars grab the opportunities to publish their research not just locally but internationally. This endeavor had such a positive impact on the development of the students in the MSU College of Education. Also, it was the first time the college was recognized and became well known for having numerous university scholars publish in international journals.

“Writing and publishing international journals is not for everyone. There's a lot of people who wants to see their studies but not given a chance to publish it. With that, producing numerous studies and published it in international journals creates an impact to the development of the students in MSU college of education. Surely, that distinction awards will not just reflect the awardee but the institution itself that we are not just excel locally but internationally.” [P#8]

“To be honest, ma'am Cathy told us that it is the 1st time that the college was recognized for having numerous university scholar for writing and publishing international journals. This recognition gave an impact to the Department/College as competitive and extra ordinary. Thus, I think more of opportunity for the college will be given and makes it will make our college well known from publishing international journals.” [P#2]

Wider Understanding on Social issues

Social issues are concerns or topics that affect a large number of people. It frequently depicts ongoing issues or disputes that are difficult to solve. Writing and publishing journals could be a way to solve and address relevant issues that our society is facing. To write and publish in international journals, two (17%) of the university scholars have said that publishing in international journals widens their understanding of social issues and helps them bridge the gap that needs a solution from which everyone can benefit.

“Since our topic is relevant to the happenings in our society, it gives meaning and awareness for our chosen field since it is very relevant. It also makes me love more of making articles that everyone can benefit on it.” [P#2]

“This boosts the Department to publish more articles to help the research society bridge the gap of those problems that needs to find a solution.” [P#7]

“For me, it improves my chosen field through those writers and authors that also advocates social problems especially for persons with disabilities.” [P#12].

University scholars also find publishing in international journals an aid to social issues that helps them improve their chosen field as teachers. Through publishing, university scholars can be able to advocate for particular social problems.

“For me, it improves my chosen field through those writers and authors that also advocates social problems especially for persons with disabilities.” [P#12]

Improved Communication

Communication is important in our daily lives because it enables us to connect with other people, share our experiences and needs, and strengthen our bonds. It gives us the opportunity to communicate our views, share information, and express our emotions. Hence, 8% of university scholars have said that publishing in international journals helps improve the communication skills of the university scholars in communicating comprehensively, as it is a crucial part for a researcher in order to clearly share information so that it will become reliable and easily make connections with the audience.

“As a future educator, being a writer gives you benefits. You can communicate clearly to your students by expressing your thoughts and opinions fluently and in a well thought out way is important. Writing will help you to improve your communication skills which will make it easier to build connections to your students.” [P#6]

Boosts self-confidence and Fuels Perseverance

The achievements and recognitions received by the university scholars after publishing in international journals give them a lot of benefits and help them improve their personal and professional development, specifically in building their self-confidence. It made them proud of themselves and encouraged them to persevere more because, through this achievement, it increased their self-confidence, which drove them to publish more articles and do better in the future.

“It can boost my confidence and it can help me to do better in the future.” [P#1] “It makes me feel confident and proud of myself because I contributed in writing a journal and it was published internationally. [P#4]

“I gained my confidence because I was able to publish a journal Internationally and helped to learn a lot of things especially when writing a journal.” [P#10]

“I am not a good writer but this weakness allows me to develop myself and make myself a better version. This journal boosted my confidence that I am capable.” [P#8]

Hence, it was clearly meant that publishing in international journals had a great impact on the university scholar's character, for it helped them regain their strength and boost their self-confidence. Upon seeing their names as authors in international journals, it was an overwhelming feeling for them. In addition, publishing in an international journal helps them do better because, for them, it is a valuable contribution as they pay back to the department that honed them to become who they are now.

“It helps to boost my confidence and knowing my purpose.” [P#12]

“For me the greatest thing for someone who's very weak in terms of writing is being noticed as someone who's good in writing. Seeing my name in an international publication is really overwhelming. It makes myself gained

more confidence. [P#6]

“It boosts my confidence and it helps me persevere more and more. Because it is really nice to contribute and give back to the Department that hone you to become who you are right now.” [P#7]

Provides Fulfillment

To be recognized and published in an international journal is a huge accomplishment for a university scholar. Given the fact that this opportunity is rare and not for everyone, it brings pride and honor to university scholars because it provides fulfillment, which benefits their personal and professional development.

“As an awardee, it gives me happiness and fulfillment because I know the difficulties, we went through to complete the journal. It also helps me strengthen my writing and analysis skills, which I will employ in my teaching career. Finally, having experience or a background in publishing a journal will benefit me professionally in the future, particularly in conducting research for the school where I will be teaching.” [P#11]

Publishing an international journal is seen as providing a number of advantages, both for the individual researcher and for society as a whole. Personal benefits of increasing thinking abilities include reasoning clarity, fresh discoveries, and personal happiness, which can lead to fulfillment as a university scholar and as a young researcher.

SOP 2. What are the struggles of student scholars on publishing?

Figure 6: Overview of the themes of university scholars struggles on publishing in international journals

Technical struggles

The joint technical struggles of university scholars in writing and publishing international Journal includes finding the RRL and forming concepts and ideas that show relevance to most people. Thus, there are 8 (67%) of university scholars who have experienced technical struggles in finding RRL in the process of making international journals and find it hard to form concepts and ideas.

“One of the struggles in writing and publishing our journal was finding RRL and at the same time the data.” [P#1]

“Struggle in the creation of journal as it becomes challenge to form concepts and ideas that shows relevance to majority of the people. Also, it needs good resources and international networks.” [P#3]

According to the participants' responses, the writing process presented them with many challenges in addition to their common difficulties. Thus, one of the main technological challenges they have faced is coming up with concepts and ideas while also looking for relevant scientific literature for their RRL. The arrangement and structure of the articles, choosing a topic, and doing a literature review were common issues mentioned by several researchers. and specifying a subject. The obstacles that prevent the participants' writing from flowing smoothly, though, are not merely technical; they also include locating reliable resources, including an internet connection.

Technological struggles

To summarize the technological struggles of university scholars in writing and publishing international journals it commonly includes the unstable internet connection where it is hard for them to find more sources of information and they only rely on data connection. The second one struggle is the lack of equipment, university scholars find it hard to not have a laptop that can be use during finding RRL and writing up session. Hence, there 3 (25%) of university scholars experienced technological struggles where it is frustrating to them to access internet connection in the sense there is no stable connection.

“I have no laptop that time. We also don't have stable internet connection when we make it. It's frustrating but I manage to overcome it.” [P#2]

“Sources of information, Internet connection and laptop, time management” [P#10]

Today's educational system is becoming more and more dependent on technology, particularly for research. Referring back to the participants' responses, they stated that the primary obstacles to completing their paper— not having a laptop and reliable internet access- make them more upset. Even though some university students do not have laptops, most still faced significant challenges because of a lack of resources and internet access. As a result, college students had to contend with technological obstacles outside of their control, like erratic internet connectivity. Additionally, inadequate technology and a poor internet connection can interfere with university scholars' writing ability. Indeed, the lack of gadgets and technology creates significant difficulties and disappointments.

Personal challenges

Under the personal challenges of the university scholars based on the data gathered, there are 6 (50%) of the university scholars experienced personal challenges that mainly included time management, lack of confidence, and priorities. Time management in the sense that university scholars are pressured on how they will manage their time. On the other hand, there is a lack of confidence; based on the result, university scholars worried that they might not meet their expectations; there were times when they could not put their thoughts into words and other times ran out of words. An added factor to lack of confidence is that they do not know how to write journals, articles, or any literature, they do not have enough ideas, and maybe they are not influenced or passionate about literature before. The third personal challenge is that they were torn on their different priorities; since they are 4th-year students, there are many tasks to do.

“As I've said, I felt the pressure during those times because it would be graded at the same time other people from another country could read it, and I worried that I might not meet their expectations. Also, there were times when I couldn't put my thoughts into words, and other times when I ran out of words”. [P#5].

“To be honest, I'm not really particular how to write journals, articles or any kind of literatures. I don't have enough ideas and maybe I was not really influenced nor passionate with literature before elementary and high school time”. [P#6] “Because I/we don't know if we are doing it correctly. [P#12]

“As I've said, I felt the pressure during those times because it would be graded at the same time other people from another country could read it, and I worried that I might not meet their expectations. Also, there were times when I couldn't put my thoughts into words, and other times when I ran out of words”. [P#5].

Writing is one of the primary language skills. It plays a significant role in expressing one's ideas, thoughts, opinions, and attitudes. Through writing, people can share ideas, feelings, persuading and convincing others. People may write for personal enjoyment or some other academic purposes. They may address an audience of one person or more persons. On the other hand, being pressured might cause a tremendous personal challenge. Thus, university scholars have a hard time when they cannot put their thoughts into words or when they run out of words, affecting their focus and emotions during their writing process. Besides, meeting other expectations could trigger the emotional aspect of the university scholars.

“To be honest, I'm not really particular how to write journals, articles or any kind of literatures. I don't have enough ideas and maybe I was not really influenced nor passionate with literature before elementary and high school time”. [P#6]

“Because I/we don't know if we are doing it correctly. [P#12]

The university scholars also experienced personal challenges during their writing journey. In light of their responses, it is clear that they struggled, especially when trying to find books or create a journal. The majority of them are unfamiliar

with the environment. Thus, they need more ideas and inspiration to write effectively. As a result, they struggled personally from the beginning of their writing career. Additionally, undergraduate students currently writing or doing research frequently feel early worry and a lack of confidence when they initially write their research papers, so there is a sense of accomplishment and pleasure once their research is finished. Moreover, common problems cited by different researchers centered on the organization and structure of the papers, defining topics, and literature review. Most research reviewed correlates language skills with academic writing.

Psychological challenges

Psychological challenges refer to the difficulties and obstacles that mobile university scholars encounter due to their finite mental processing ability. Hence, the root cause of their struggles in writing and publishing scholarly work under psychological challenges is the total data of 2 (17%), including worries, pressure, and emotionally stressed. University scholars felt worried because they were not good at constructing grammar, and that is the standard error that their mentor/research adviser returned their paper. The second challenge is that they felt pressured while writing the journal. Also, it was their first time publishing a paper, and they needed to learn how to do it properly. However, thanks to their studies' guidance and help, university scholars guided them to publish their papers internationally. Moreover, based on the result of the respondents, university scholars experienced emotionally stressed on how they will deal with the responsibilities at school at the same time at home.

“Because I am not that good in grammar and these are our common error that's why Ma'am Cath returned our paper”. [P#7]

“We actually struggle during the process but not in publishing the paper because there's someone who helped us do the study and guided us to surely publish the study” [P#8]

“It was my first time publish a paper and I don't know how to properly do it but thanks to Ma'am Cathy for helping us out and giving us the opportunity to publish it”. [P#10].

Student life can be stressful, and for some students, it may cause mental distress; mental distress can influence academic achievement. Undergraduate students, most especially university scholars, who are doing research, reported a lack of confidence and initial anxiety when they first wrote their research papers. There is a sense of success and pride after completing their research paper, especially when someone is there to help and guide them throughout their journey. On the other hand, the mentor's help and guidance are a way to help their students improve their research papers and likewise help students cope with challenges. Hence, in critiquing writing samples from the university, scholars help the students decipher the correct way of writing and discussing part of their paper. Mentors' factors also have a significant role to play. They must motivate their students to write well, and they should believe in the ability of the students to create a change.

“We struggle because we are besieged with responsibilities from other subjects that we also need to attend to at that time, and it is difficult to perform everything at once. Not just the tasks that we have at school but also the tasks that we have at home. [P#11]

The university scholars experienced lots of workloads to do. In today's 21st century, where innovative and curriculum learning takes place, many individual tasks exist. The university scholars were torn and besieged with their responsibilities at home and school. Thus, they encountered psychological challenges, affecting their finite mental processing ability and time management. On the other hand, time management has helped people organize their professional lives for centuries. The existing literature, however, reveals mixed findings and a lack of clarity as to whether, when, how, and why time management leads to critical outcomes such as well-being and job performance. The reality, however, is that people who manage their time are, like all people, embedded in an intricate web of social relationships and constraints.

Noisy Environment

Another problem university scholars face is the noisy environment that affects the momentum of their writing process. The noisy environment could also bring more distractions. There 1 (8%) of the university scholars experienced the cause distractions of the noisy environment; they were at their homes or respective boarding houses while writing the journals. More distractors from their environment will enable them to have difficulty focusing, thinking, writing, and continuously doing some research.

“These are the common problems I encountered, first lack of equipment, unstable internet connection, noisy environment, lack of focus and more of distractors”. [P#8]

Environmental noise is also a pivotal problem that university scholars encounter during their writing process journey. Any undesired sound produced by human activity that is thought to be damaging to human health and quality of life is referred to as environmental noise (King, 2022). In residential neighborhoods, traffic is the main cause of noise disturbance, followed by nearby residents. Numerous research show that non-auditory stress consequences from traffic noise include physiological system alterations, numerous cognitive impairments, sleep difficulties, social behavior changes, psychosocial stress-related symptoms, and emotional and motivational problems. However, university students are frequently subjected to distracting sounds when working at home or in their various boarding homes, which can be troublesome because background noise typically impairs cognitive function. The writer's capacity to focus is also greatly impacted by this outside noise, which makes them lose focus and become distracted all the time.

SOP 3. What motivates student scholars on publishing their scholarly works?

Figure 7: Overview of the themes of university scholars' motivation on publishing in international journals.

Requirement

Submitting a thesis can earn your bachelor's degree. Writing a thesis, for instance, maybe a degree requirement in some universities. It serves as a way to demonstrate learning during the program of study and may contribute to the body of research in areas of specialization. Some 17% of University Scholars said that they see writing a thesis as one requirement to graduate in the first place, but they enjoy it afterward.

“It’s one of our requirements and imagine how it end up.” [P#1]

“To be honest, one of the factors is that it was one of the requirements in one subject, but along the way, I am starting to enjoy it.” [P#2]

To obtain a bachelor's degree, a thesis must be submitted. Based on the participants' responses, 17%, of Participant #1 said they were motivated to do a thesis since it was a requirement. A student's undergraduate thesis comprises written materials that broaden the level of understanding of the issue and assist in solving it. University scholars stated that they are driven to write and complete their thesis since it is required. It has always been the practice to have the thesis hardbound before students may be certified as graduates and have their names added to the list. The graduate student's motivation for achievement is their desire to complete a degree thesis.

Encouragement

A total of 42% who prompted University Scholars to write because they are inspired and encouraged by their research adviser.

“First of all, it is the thesis adviser who pushes us and sees that our research paper has something special....” [P#4]

“Encourage by the professor to continue doing it....” [P#3]

“The desire to hear our ideas. Aside from that, we are encouraged by our professor to do such study.” [P#8]

“...we are encouraging by our professor to do such study...” [P#11]

“....it is because of our professor...” [P#12]

According to the participants, P#3, P#8, P#11, and P#12 stated that they were inspired to write their study because their thesis adviser encouraged them. For them, their adviser sees potential in them and pushes them beyond their comfort zones. Moreover, P#4 responded that their thesis adviser pushed them because their thesis adviser saw significance in their paper. Writing and publishing an international journal is a tremendous process. Throughout the process, it needs constant encouragement. The adviser or mentor guides the researchers and inspires them to reach their fullest potential. University Scholars frequently internalize encouraging remarks and behaviors, which might inspire them to succeed.

Recognition

They considered that publishing an international journal leads to a broader audience who can access it. Another motivation for University Scholars' is Recognition. There are 8% of total respondents said they are motivated to write and publish in International Journals because they want to be recognized. Others are made to feel proud for belonging to a well-known and esteemed group. Additionally, distributing published works to enormous scope of audience enables them to comprehend market difficulties and answers.

“To make our paper recognized and to inspire our respondents.” [P#7]

“To be honest, I have no interest in writing or making articles or journals. I never even joined contest in my former school regarding on making journals such as journalism. What makes me encourage is the time that my work was being recognized by our professor and in that way, it encourages me to continue doing it.” [P#3]

According to Participant #7, one of the key reasons the University Scholars published an international journal was to be acknowledged and to motivate other researchers. It is obvious that publishing globally allows for reaching a large audience. Additionally, participant #3 stated that they had little interest in producing articles or journals and had never even entered a contest at their previous schools to become journalists. When the professor acknowledges their work, it inspires and motivates them to keep going. University scholars need help to realize where they have come from. Although they might not be interested in writing, the adviser's acknowledgment and recognition of their job is essential.

Legacy

Writing and Publishing an International Journal can give a chance to leave a legacy that inspires people to strive hard and could be a source of motivation for others. A total of 8% who had said that they prompted to write and publish international journals to leave a legacy.

“The opportunity to be able to publish the paper and to leave a legacy to contribute to the development of the department.” [P#10]

The increasing number of publications speaks about how they contribute to the department where they belong. It is evident how the department molds them to be influential writers and great problem solvers wherein they can publish international journals. Based on the participants' answers, it is an excellent opportunity to publish the paper and leave a legacy that contributed to the development of the department. Leaving a legacy is important for many reasons. While serving as a role model for future generations, it may help to preserve memories and convey valuable life lessons. Being able to motivate and inspire individuals to strive for greatness despite their circumstances is a source of pride.

Knowledge contributor

One of the reasons why University Scholars publish journals is because they want to inform. Writing in a journal lets you focus on finding a solution and helps you understand your issues—sharing thoughts, problems, and feelings with others.

“Our articles are all stories amidst Covid-19. So, I think it's really relevant and there's a need to published those articles for the next generation and so on. To know what we experienced and how we did survive.” [P#1]

“To share my ideas and experiences with others, to express my thoughts or ideas on a particular topic, and to fulfill my dream.” [P#2]

“To make our paper discover by other researchers” [P#7]

“To share my piece and show it to others, you can publish it too.” [P#9]

“Initially, it was merely our advisers desire to publish and for compliance, but as we continued to work together, I realized that I wanted to publish it because I want to help other researchers gain answers and insights from our journal.” [P#11]

“I honestly don’t know. I just give my best in writing. For me, the reason why our research adviser chose my/our article to publish was to share our experiences as a student in the midst of pandemic and how we cope up.” [P#12]

“Hear student voice and struggles that will allow everyone see how they triumph” [P#8]

“To share my ideas and experiences with others, to express my thoughts or ideas on a particular topic, and to fulfill my dream.” [P#2]

Publishing an International Journal is an opportunity to share ideas and want to inform others. As P #1 responded that publishing journals could be an avenue to help future generations. In addition, P#7 responded that publishing the paper helped to discover the other researcher. Publication of work through accessible sources aids in learning for others. It helps to increase the body of knowledge in the chosen field by adding experiences to the literature on the topic. Furthermore, based on the response of P#8, Publishing International Journal can hear students' voices and hardships, enabling everyone to observe their successes. International Journals can help people better understand issues, hear from struggling people, and discuss problems and possible solutions.

Show competence

Competence is the capacity to act successfully. A person can complete a task or job successfully. Being competent means an individual has sufficient skills and knowledge. There are 32% of University Scholars desire to write.

“To be honest, I did not expect that one of my articles will be recognized as one of the best journals, so it is not my reason why it was published but it is the help of our Almighty God and our professor in making it possible to publish internationally.” [P#3]

“Aside from adding this to my curriculum vitae, it also helps me to trust and believe in myself that I can do things that smart people can do.” [P#10].

According to P #3, they did not expect to have their work published internationally. Sometimes writing journals demonstrate one's abilities. Their writing abilities, which are genuinely visible in their work, were used throughout the process. In addition, as P#10 responded, it could be added to their curriculum vitae and help to develop confidence in one's ability to match that of others. It certainly is a chance to be listed on the curriculum vitae. Although publishing a journal might be challenging, the results are worthwhile.

Help the community

Through research, it performs a crucial social function responsive to a recognized need. It gives accurate and timely information about a population's needs, attitudes, and motivations. It is the source of all information and offers solutions to issues; 8% of the University Scholars have said that helping the community makes them want to write.

“You got to write and contribute to a published journal and will then give help to the community.” [P#5].

Based on the response, P#5, you got to write and contribute to a published journal and will then give help to the community. Publishing journals give an avenue to help the community, just like seeing a problem in the community and giving a solution to it. To comprehend, broaden one's understanding, and acquire knowledge for one's social life.

Stand out in the job market

Writing and Publishing International Journal stands out in the job market. That leads to growing professionally. There are 8% of University scholars who had responded that Writing and Publishing journals help them to grow professionally and stand out in the job market.

“As a future educator, this kind of achievement is an advantage if I’m going to apply to some schools. Just like the time that I decided to find a work, someone personal message me if I could apply to their school cause they

really in a need of teachers who is competent in writing.” [P#1]

Knowing that University Scholars' attitudes in doing research can lead to success and growth. This achievement in publishing international journals, such as standing out in the job market, means being ahead of another applicant. Publishing journals speaks about how competent a person is in writing. Since applying job requires specific skills that one should possess. As P#1 had responded, someone's message about finding work is because they need a teacher who is competent in writing. It is evident that when publishing a journal, there are so many opportunities knocks, especially when it is about work.

Future professions

Planning for future professions is essential to make informed choices about future career jobs. University Scholars see themselves five years from now as researchers (50%), teacher-researcher (25%), teaching field (8%), influencers 8%, and lawmaker (8%).

“I see myself as a teacher who’s working for her master’s degree.” [P#1]

“In the teaching field utilizing the things I have experienced in my recent years.” [P#4]

“An independent research writer. A proficient one.” [P#5]

“In teacher education field and apply learnings to publish more studies to help generation by generation.” [P#8]

“I see myself pursuing more research related to peacebuilding and other related concerns here in our local community.” [P#9]

“I see myself in five years still writing relevant articles and researches that could address social issues.” [P#10]

“5 years from now, I can see myself being able to publish more works and to attend more seminars to help me improve in this field.” [P#11]

“Aside from working as an educator, I am looking forward to publish another article from my master's degree.” [P#2]

“As I've said earlier that I am not really into writing but thinking of what will I be after five years? Maybe, I see myself working with another one? Am may not being that influential person but I'll try my best give another one shot.” [P#3]

“I consider myself happy and successful in my chosen profession, and I hope to have the opportunity to publish again in a journal that will help other researchers.” [P#12]

“I see myself as successful individual who’s able to Influence the youth and people, to always do their best.” [P#6]

“I think I will be a mayor.” [P#7]

University Scholars see themselves five years from now as a researcher as the responded of P#3 to give it a try five years from now, P#5 also added to be an independent research writer, P#9 want to pursue more research related to peacebuilding and other concerns in the local community. Moreover, P#10 also added to still writing relevant articles five years from now, like P#11 and P#12, to publish more work. The University Scholars see their achievement as their training ground to publish more since they are le to start it. On the other hand, P#2, P#1, and P#8 said they want to be teacher- researchers. They are in the teacher education field and published another article. P#1 in the teaching field, P#6 as an influencer, and P#7 as a politician. Planning plans is necessary; the direction to take is a path toward the future. Nobody can predict the future. Thoughts on what is essential now and in the future? The more we can do to prepare for potential challenges, the better.

5.2. Discussion

Publishing research results in international publications is a substantial endeavor for university scholars. It is an essential channel for communicating their intellectual achievements and advancing collective knowledge in their particular domains. International journals are considered as having a very prominent scientific role. They act as the porters of

credible science and disseminate it to the widest possible audience (Murudkar, 2022). However, this process is fraught with difficulties, and researchers frequently experience both triumphs and struggles along the route.

Based on the analysis of the gathered data of this study, the findings indicated that university scholars' experiences in their triumphs in publishing internationally are rewarding, expand the writer's credentials, provide a more comprehensive understanding of social issues, promote high morale and honor, improve writing and pedagogical philosophy, develop technical skills in exploring interweaving ideas, improve communication, fuel perseverance, and provide fulfillment.

The result implies that the experiences of the university scholars after publishing their scholarly works in international journals brought them several triumphs in their academic achievements in terms of developing their technical skills in exploring interweaving ideas and comprehensive understanding of social issues. It also brought success in their personal growth in terms of improving their communication, being perseverant in all what they do and providing fulfillment in themselves. Furthermore, it brought them professional development which expands the university scholars' credentials, promotes their high morale and honor, and it improves their writing and pedagogical philosophy (Smith & Thompson, 2019), investigate the experiences of early-career researchers in publishing internationally. The study highlights the triumphs associated with publishing, such as gaining recognition and contributing to the field. Thus, the triumphs experienced by the university scholars on publishing in international journals is rewarding which brought them high recognitions in their academic endeavors.

Furthermore, university scholars also faced struggles publishing in international journals when it came to technology, they encountered unstable internet connection and lack of equipment that they were going to use on their writing process. On the other hand, the personal struggles experienced were time management, a lack of financial support, and perseverance. Thus, young scholars also experienced psychological challenges. They felt worries, pressure, and at the same time emotionally stressed on the process of their writing the journals. Nevertheless, they encountered environmental problems, as a result, the university scholar's ability to focus and maintain their momentum while writing for their required international journals is affected by the noisy surroundings. Meanwhile, university scholars also needed help in technical writing in terms of finding RRL, forming concepts and ideas, and grammar.

Additionally, university scholars are affected mainly by the struggles they have experienced during the writing and publishing of their scholarly works. The findings indicated that university scholars' needed help in technical writing in terms of finding RRL, forming concepts and ideas, and grammar. Due to a lack of proficiency in English, they may not have had the necessary experience writing and publishing their research articles in reputable publications (Moldovan, 2011). Furthermore, a lot of students continue to make grammatical mistakes that take up a lot of the lecturer's time and energy to fix their written assignments, according to Susana Jamian et al. (2006). After examining the students' writing faults, it appears that they make a variety of grammatical problems, including local, global, and spelling mistakes. Their numerous grammatical errors in L2 writing reflect their lack of understanding. According to Agostino (2022), even while college students were generally tech-savvy, the study revealed that many of them struggled with uncontrollable technology issues like erratic internet availability. However, it seems that all students benefit from supportive technology created for students with impairments.

Based on the study, the researchers revealed that university scholars' motivation on publishing in international journals are the mentors' encouragement and recognition, show competence, requirement, stand out in the job market, knowledge contributors, help the community, future professions and leave a legacy to the writers, department, and university. The result implies that writing for publication has several aspects of motivation for University Scholars. That helps them to strengthen their skills and positivity as authors. University Scholars may vary their definition of success when it comes to motivation but they are one with their goals in which to publish international journals and to disseminate research findings in a widest possible audience.

This study also aimed to dig deeper about the University scholars' motivation on publishing in international journals. It highlights their motivation and experiences. The study's findings suggest five key motivations for submitting articles, namely: contributing to the profession, journal recognition, their desire to accomplish a goal, the assurance of receiving assistance in such an attempt, and some practical motivations. Above all, the major motivator is the belief that they can and should contribute to the profession as teachers. Our participants, like Smiles and Short (2006), demonstrated that their decision to publish an article was to inform the field by presenting an intellectual or expert perspective. Study revealed that interest is still another strong motivator. Accordingly, it serves two main purposes: it influences students' goals, particularly if they see writing as a means of satisfying their communication needs (Csikszentmihalyi & Rathunde, 2000)

Along with the discussion, the authors suggested that future university scholars should possess and invest in the following attributes to write and publish an international journal; hardworking, an opportunity taker, courageous, calm, efficient, and perseverance. Increasing self-awareness, confidence, and motivation contributed to a sense of accomplishment and pleasure in writing (Grant & Knowles, 2004). Another suggestion is that to the advisers and teachers, by encouraging students' autonomy, relevance, relatedness, competency, instructors' interests in the subject, and self-efficacy, teachers can improve their students' motivation to learn (Gu et al., 2012). Although motivation can be intrinsic or extrinsic, teachers must create a setting that inspires students to learn. Teachers play a crucial role in fostering a climate encouraging students to learn. They frequently encourage pupils' independence (Schuitema et al., 2016). By encouraging

their freedom of choice, teachers help students identify with their own. Additionally, granlso recognizing pupils for their work, progress, and cooperation can boost their self-esteem, give them a sense of success, and earn their peers' respect. Improvement is stimulated by feeling this sense of accomplishment (Olinger, 2018).

6. CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on academic publishing by offering a grounded and human-centered understanding of how university scholars navigate both the rewards and challenges of publishing in international journals. By focusing on the lived experiences of student scholars, the study goes beyond technical discussions of writing and highlights the emotional, psychological, and developmental dimensions of the publication journey. It provides valuable insights into how publishing not only strengthens research competence and academic writing skills but also shapes identity, confidence, and professional aspirations among future educators. In doing so, the study amplifies student voices that are often underrepresented in scholarly discourse and offers a more holistic perspective on what it truly means to become a researcher in today's academic environment.

7. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study carry important implications for higher education institutions, research mentors, and aspiring scholars. They suggest that publishing success is not solely dependent on individual capability but is deeply influenced by the availability of institutional support, mentorship, and access to resources. In line with Toquero (2021), universities must adopt inclusive and flexible strategies that address both technological and pedagogical challenges faced by student researchers. This includes strengthening digital infrastructure, providing accessible research tools, and fostering supportive academic communities. For educators, the study highlights the need to guide students not only in research skills but also in building resilience, confidence, and motivation. Ultimately, strengthening these support systems can empower more student researchers to participate in global scholarly conversations and contribute meaningful knowledge to society.

8. CONCLUSION

This study examined the triumphs and struggles of university scholars in publishing in international, Scopus-indexed journals and revealed that scholarly publication is both a rewarding achievement and a demanding academic endeavour. The findings demonstrate that successful publication significantly enhances scholars' academic credibility, professional growth, and contribution to knowledge production. Participants reported that publishing strengthened their research competence, refined their academic writing and pedagogical perspectives, expanded their professional credentials, and fostered a sense of fulfilment and institutional pride. These triumphs underscore the transformative impact of international publication on individual scholars and the broader academic community.

However, the study also identified persistent and multifaceted challenges encountered throughout the publication process. Technical difficulties related to literature review development, conceptual framing, and academic language proficiency were prominent concerns. Technological constraints, including unstable internet connectivity and limited access to specialized research tools, further complicated the process. Personal and institutional barriers—such as time management pressures, insufficient financial support, and inadequate research infrastructure—exacerbated these challenges. Psychological factors, including stress, anxiety, and publication pressure, particularly affected early-career scholars. Environmental distractions and limited dedicated research spaces likewise hindered sustained scholarly productivity.

Despite these obstacles, scholars' motivation remained strong, driven by mentorship support, professional recognition, aspirations for career advancement, and a desire to contribute meaningful knowledge to society. The findings highlight the critical role of institutional support systems in sustaining research productivity. To enhance publication outcomes in Scopus-indexed journals, higher education institutions should strengthen mentorship programs, establish structured recognition mechanisms (e.g., research excellence awards), develop clear criteria for research distinction, and create dedicated research hubs equipped with adequate facilities. Furthermore, expanding access to international training and research seminars can build scholarly capacity and global engagement. Strengthening these structural and motivational supports is essential for fostering a sustainable research culture and increasing international research visibility.

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